
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

OFFSITE MEETING

APRIL 12TH – APRIL 13TH 2024
OLOMOUC, CZECH REPUBLIC

INSTITUTE FOR CLINICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE
INSTITUTE OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY AND BIOCHEMISTRY OF THE CAS
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOLOGY OF THE CAS
MASARYK UNIVERSITY
CHARLES UNIVERSITY

The project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

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Dear colleagues,

the National Institute for Research on Cardiovascular Diseases Related to Metabolic Diseases of Diabetes and Obesity (the CarDia project) gives many teams from the 5 participating institutions the opportunity to meet, get to know each other to some extent and establish new cooperations. One of the ways are the so-called OffSite meetings, which take us out of the daily routine and allow us to share interesting, often priority results in a nice place away from our workplaces, as well as to establish personal relationships in a social time after the scientific presentations. I would like to express my enthusiasm for the opportunity to get a view into the activities of the participating professional groups from FGU, UOCHB, UK, MU and IKEM, which I might never have known about otherwise. I also appreciate the efforts of my colleagues who, in more than 50 lectures and posters, choose to present their impressive results in a way that was accessible to others who are specialists in other fields.

Our seemingly very broad cross-section between cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders, including the development of new methods for their study, covers well the pathogenetic continuity of these diseases. Currently, metabolic disorders are largely a consequence of modern lifestyles, including inadequate nutrition and unnaturally low physical activity in the populations of developed countries, and cardiovascular diseases can be considered the most serious consequence of uncontrolled metabolic diseases according to current knowledge.

The CarDia project therefore provides an opportunity to bring together teams involved in the prevention and treatment of metabolic disorders and the therapy of their often-life-threatening complications. I firmly believe that this collaboration will provide a wealth of new insights into the nature and treatment of these diseases and thus contribute to reducing the mortality they cause.

We wish you to enjoy your stay and meet nice people in Olomouc,

Martin Haluzík,

Principal Investigator of the CarDia
project

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WP1 Prevention of obesity, diabetes and cardiovascular complications

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 1

Group of Genetics of Model Diseases, Institute of Physiology, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague
Principal Investigator: Ing. Michal Pravenec, DrSc.

Abstract:

Recently, we have identified a recessive mutation, an abnormal coat appearance in the BXH6 strain, a member of the HXB/BXH set of recombinant inbred (RI) strains. The RI strains were derived from the spontaneously hypertensive rat (SHR) and Brown Norway rat (BN-Lx) progenitors. Whole genome sequencing of the mutant rats identified the 195875980 G/A mutation in the tuftelin 1 (Tuft1) gene on chromosome 2, which resulted in a premature stop codon. Compared with wild-type BXH6 rats, BXH6-Tuft1 mutant rats exhibited lower body weight due to reduced visceral fat and ectopic fat accumulation in the liver and heart. Reduced adiposity was associated with decreased serum glucose and insulin and increased insulin-stimulated glycogenesis in skeletal muscle. In addition, mutant rats had lower serum monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 and leptin levels, indicative of reduced inflammation. Analysis of the liver proteome identified differentially expressed proteins from fatty acid metabolism and β -oxidation, peroxisomes, carbohydrate metabolism, inflammation, and proteasome pathways.

Summary: These results provide evidence for the important role of the Tuft1 gene in the regulation of lipid and glucose metabolism and suggest underlying molecular mechanisms.

This study was performed by collaboration of 3 institutions within the CarDia project.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 1

Research group Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Faculty of Medicine, MUNI, Brno
Principal Investigator: Prof. Kateřina Kaňková, M.D., Ph.D.

Abstract:

Recent epidemiological data in Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) highlight significant challenges as women in developed countries are older and with higher BMI at the time of pregnancy, both factors facilitating the increasing prevalence of GDM. While in majority of cases GDM normalizes after delivery, persistent glucose intolerance (PGI) might persist in some posing a considerable risk for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular diseases in following period.

Our recent studies ascertained the prevalence of metabolic syndrome (MetSy) in GDM women and correlation with/predictive power for the PGI. The data reveal that (i) a significant percentage of women

with GDM exhibit traits of MetSy, (ii) MetSy is highly prevalent in women with PGI and (ii) diagnosis of MetSy is associated with increased risks of macrosomia and other selected perinatal complications.

Additionally, we recently analysed genetic architecture of GDM and PGI through the construction of genetic risk scores (GRSs) derived from GWAS-identified T2DM markers and explored their predictive potential for adverse GDM outcomes. Comparison of GRS distribution in T2DM, GDM and non-diabetic controls indicate similarity between genetics of T2DM and GDM and also predictive power of GRS for PGI.

These recent data support the predictive power of genetic factors for postpartum stratification of GDM subjects (since only approx. 50% of women participate in current postpartum screening based on oGTT). We plan to extend the genetic analyses and to re-evaluate our previously developed/published score "FOBDIT" enriched by genetic parameters and to analyse its power in independent replication cohort.

Summary:

Our recent research indicates that women with GDM face a high risk of persistent post-pregnancy glucose intolerance and GDM in this subset may represent T2DM first manifested in pregnancy. It is highly desirable to predict the risk of PGI as early as second trimester of pregnancy and personalise the postpartum management accordingly to prevent cardiometabolic consequences of undiagnosed diabetes.

Acknowledgements:

This presentation and the research were made possible by collaboration among Masaryk University, University Hospitals in Brno, IKEM and the Institute of Endocrinology in Prague, highlighting a multidisciplinary approach to tackling GDM and its long-term effects.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 1

Laboratory of Adipose Tissue Biology IPHYS, Prague
Principal Investigator: MUDr. Martin Rossmeisl, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Previous studies have identified palmitic acid esters of hydroxystearic acid (PAHSA) as lipokines with potent anti-inflammatory and insulin sensitizing properties. We found that chronic exercise in humans increases PAHSA levels in adipose tissue and in the circulation. However, it is not known how acute exercise affects the release of PAHSA or other lipokines of the hydroxy fatty acid ester (FAHFA) family from adipose tissue and whether this process is affected by obesity or aging.

We subjected male C57BL/6J mice (groups of lean, obese and aged animals) to a single bout of treadmill exercise after 4 hours of fasting. In obese and aged mice, exercise-induced lipolysis activation was attenuated, as evidenced by *ex vivo* analysis of adipose tissue lipolytic activity and measurement of non-esterified fatty acids in the circulation. At the same time, visceral adipose tissue explants showed a higher degree of exercise-induced lipolytic activation than those of subcutaneous adipose tissue. As expected, obesity and aging were associated with significant reductions in baseline FAHFA levels in adipose tissue and circulation, which was related to differences in the expression of genes involved in adipose tissue FAHFA metabolism. While acute exercise increased adipose tissue levels of various FAHFA/PAHSA regioisomers only in lean mice, circulating FAHFA/PAHSA levels remained largely unchanged in all groups.

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Summary: The response of white adipose tissue to acute exercise in terms of lipolysis activation and increased FAHFA levels is impaired in obese and aged mice.

The acute exercise experiments performed with CarDia support will be crucial for our planned activities to unravel the mechanisms regulating FAHFA/PAHSA synthesis and release in adipose tissue.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 1

Early life social conditions and adverse experiences predict longitudinal relations between childhood BMI and overeating

Recetox, Masaryk University, Brno
Principal Investigator: Martin Bobák

Abstract:

The progression of obesity is a continuous process involving a complex system of genetic, environmental, and behavioural factors that influence an individual's susceptibility to excess adiposity. Socioeconomic disadvantage as well as psychological distress may lead to overeating, in this context typically referred to as emotional overeating. We assume that overeating leads to increased energy intake, followed by weight gain, however, recent evidence indicated that the association between childhood obesity and overeating might be bidirectional. This bidirectional relationship gives rise to the hypothesis that overeating and BMI as interconnected drivers of childhood obesity, may be predicted by different upstream determinants. Therefore, this study aimed to longitudinally investigate the directionality of the association between childhood BMI and overeating and to identify antecedent early childhood predictors.

The study sample included data of 5,151 children (born 1991 – 1992) from the European Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ELSPAC), collected between 18 months and 11 years of child age. The outcomes were child BMI and overeating. Predictors included maternal BMI, maternal education, single-parent households, financial difficulties, and adverse childhood experiences (ACEs). The random intercept cross-lagged panel model (RI-CLPM) was applied.

The results showed temporal stability in the development of overeating and BMI, with a bidirectional relationship that strengthened over time. The child's BMI was predicted by maternal BMI. The child's overeating was predicted by maternal BMI, but a stronger effect was found for ACEs. ACEs mediated the impact of maternal education, financial difficulties, and single parenthood on overeating.

Summary:

We observed stable bidirectional longitudinal effects, with a stronger association from BMI to overeating than in the opposite direction. Childhood obesity resulted from two main pathways: one linked to maternal BMI and early childhood BMI increase followed by overeating, and the other associated with ACEs mediating the effect of early childhood socioeconomic factors on overeating, leading to gradual BMI gain.

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WP2 New treatment options for diabetes and obesity and their complications

**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Title:

New analogs of neuropeptides for treatment of obesity and type 2 diabetes

Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry and Institute of Physiology, Czech Academy of Sciences,
Prague

Principal Investigator: RNDr. Lenka Maletínská, DSc.

Abstract:

Recently discovered anorexigenic neuropeptides, such as prolactin-releasing peptide (PrRP) and cocaine- and amphetamine-regulated transcript (CART) peptide, represent new trends in development of anti-obesity agents. Neuropeptides are released and acting directly in brain areas regulating food intake, but generally do not cross the blood-brain barrier if administered peripherally. We succeeded to design stable lipidized analogs of PrRP with prolonged acute anorexigenic effect after peripheral administration in mice and rats. Repeated peripheral administration of the lipidized PrRP analogs resulted in long-lasting anti-obesity and antidiabetic effects in rodent models of diet induced obesity and insulin resistance. Moreover, our newly designed and synthesized lipidized analogs of CART peptide showed also very strong food intake lowering properties in mouse model of diet induced obesity.

Besides anorexigenic peptides, also antagonists and inverse agonists of peripherally released and centrally acting orexigenic peptide ghrelin are candidates for anti-obesity treatment. Recently, liver-enriched antimicrobial peptide (LEAP2) as an endogenous ghrelin antagonist/ inverse agonist was discovered and we explore its possible role in organism as well as anti-obesity properties of newly designed shortened LEAP2 analogs lipidized at C-terminus. These analogs showed high affinity to ghrelin receptor and antagonistic/inverse agonistic features when antagonizing orexigenic effect of ghrelin in mice. Moreover, palmitoylated LEAP2 analog showed increased stability in mouse plasma and prolonged pharmacokinetics in mice.

Summary:

We showed that lipidization of anorexigenic peptides might be an effective way to transmit the desired effect to the central nervous system after peripheral administration in preclinical rodent models, for a potential treatment of obesity and related complications such as Type 2 diabetes.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Chemistry of Bioconjugates group IOCB, Prague
Principal Investigator: Ing. Milan Vrábek, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Pyruvate is a key intermediate in glucose metabolism. It enters the mitochondria where it is converted into acetyl-CoA by the pyruvate dehydrogenase complex. Acetyl-CoA then enters the tricarboxylic acid cycle to produce energy in the form of ATP. Dysregulation of this process can lead to insulin resistance, a hallmark of type 2 diabetes.

To develop an approach for quantifying pyruvate levels within living cells, we engineered a novel, biocompatible mitochondrial CF₃TPP Mito probe. Upon activation, this probe facilitates the selective labeling of diverse keto metabolites, including pyruvate, within this organelle. Subsequently, these labeled metabolites can be accurately detected using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry. To streamline and improve the efficiency of the labeling process, we also developed the next generation of activators. These activators are about 100 times more efficient in the activation of Mito probe when compared to previously used derivatives.

Summary:

Combination of the non-toxic CF₃TPP Mito probe with new activators does not influence the normal physiology of cells and allows efficient tagging and subsequent analysis of the labeled pyruvate in LC-MS experiments.

Selected sample of data obtained with CarDia support demonstrated the functioning techniques providing useful data for planned activities.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Laboratory of Translational and Experimental Diabetology and Obezitology IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. Martin Haluzík, DrSc.

Targeting senescence as a new promising approach in treatment of metabolic diseases

Sona Stemberkova Hubackova¹, Jan Stursa², Lukas Werner², Michaela Rennerova¹, Iveta Pleyerova¹,
Tereza Havrlantova¹, Petr Svoboda¹, Barbora Judita Kasperova², Renata Pavlovicova¹, Miloslava
Cechova¹, Martin Haluzik^{1,2}

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¹Centre for Experimental Medicine, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic, ²Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

Introduction: Obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) represent a major health problems with increasing prevalence worldwide. Limited efficacy of current therapies have prompted a search for novel therapeutic options. Changes induced by long-standing, poorly controlled obesity followed by the development of T2DM are linked to premature senescence in various tissues, contributing to further deterioration of their function and eventually to the development of chronic irreversible complications. Since mitochondria play a key role in development and maintenance of cellular senescence, our goal was to develop new, tamoxifen independent mitochondria-targeted senolytic agents and test their potential to improve metabolic diseases and pathologies related to T2DM.

Methods: C57BL/6 male mice (n=8-10) fed with SD (standard diet for 8 month), HFD (high fat diet for 8 month) were treated with MitoTam (MT; 2 mg/kg dissolved in 4 % ethanol in corn oil), compound X (2mg/kg dissolved in 4 % ethanol in corn oil) or the vehicle (CO) given i.p. twice per week for a period of 4 weeks.

Results: Our data show, that compared to non-treated mice HFD mice compound X improved glucose parameters, reduced body weight and adipose tissue mass similarly as previously used MitoTam. Glucose-lowering effect of compound X was linked to improvement of T2DM-related hormones profile and was accompanied by reduced lipid accumulation in liver. Lower senescent cell burden in various tissues also resulted in lower level of circulating inflammatory mediators that enhance metabolic dysfunction. Moreover, decreased presence of senescent cells reduced pancreatic fibrosis, a frequently occurring complication of T2DM that worsen its progression. Mice treated with compound X showed lower accumulation of fibrotic cells in pancreas followed by decreased inflammation and improvement of hyperinsulinemia. Compound X also showed direct effect on reduction of pancreatic adenocarcinoma compared to MitoTam. This indicates, that compound X reduces not only risk of development of pancreatitis, but also prevents/reduces risk of development of pancreatic cancer.

Conclusions: Mitochondria-targeted senolytic agents represent promising therapy for metabolic diseases and prevention of their chronic complications including cancers development.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Group of Diabetic Foot Care and CVD Risk Group IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. MUDr. Michal Dubský, Ph.D., FRSPH, MBA

Abstract:

Autologous cell therapy (ACT) is a new therapeutic approach for the treatment of critical limb ischemia. We improved the isolation and separation technique because of the new laminar box bought from CarDia project. ACT has been proven to increase transcutaneous oxygen pressure, decrease pain, improve wound healing, and decrease the rate of major amputation in diabetic patients with severe ischemia. Recently we compared two different ischemia porcine models – ischemic flap and ischemic limbs by means of transcutaneous oxygen pressure and vessel index assess histologically.

Cardiovascular risk group investigated 12 asymptomatic patients with high risk due to carotid plaques and high calcium score and those patients underwent optical coherent tomography of their coronary arteries. In 4/12 patients we observed very high-risk plaque and in 7/12 patients we saw thin cap fibroatheroma. 11/12 patients were treated by siRNA inhibitor inclisiran to reduce plasmatic levels of their lipids.

Summary: Autologous cells therapy increased ischemia parameters in patients with ineligible severe ischemia of the foot, ischemic flaps proved to be the most severe porcine model of critical limb ischemia. We demonstrated that optical coherent tomography could reveal a very dangerous plaques in asymptomatic people with type 1 diabetes.

These new diagnostic and therapeutic approaches with CarDia support demonstrated the functioning techniques providing useful data for planned activities.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Laboratory of Pain research, Institute of Physiology, Academy of Science of the Czech Republic, Prague
Principal Investigator: Jiri Palecek MD, PhD.

Abstract: Physiological pain is an important biological mechanism designed to protect organism from potentially harmful stimuli. Pathological states, such as painful diabetic neuropathy, characterized by allodynia, hyperalgesia and spontaneous chronic pain, on the other hand can become debilitating diseases, often recalcitrant to the best available treatment efforts. The existing analgesic treatments also bring serious side effects that have deleterious effects on the patient's life and may also lead to other health problems. There is a clear and urgent need for new, mechanism based analgesic treatments. In our experiments we have studied the role of endogenous agonists of cannabinoid (CB1) and vanilloid (TRPV1) receptors in modulation of nociception at the spinal cord level and their role in development of painful diabetic neuropathy. Our published data show that application of anandamide precursor 20:4 NAPE leads to increased production of anandamide, an endogenous agonists of CB1 and TRPV1 receptors. Such as treatment has better analgesic effect probably due to local specific synthesis of anandamide, compared to direct anandamide application. Using model of diabetic neuropathy, our results show significant potentiation of neuroinflammation in the nociceptive pathway following High Fat diet.

Summary: Our data support the role of endogenous CB1 and TRPV1 receptors agonists in modulation of neuropathic pain. High fat diet potentiates painful conditions in peripheral neuropathy.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2**

Laboratory of Adipose Tissue Biology, IPHYS, Prague
Mgr. Kristina Bardová, Ph.D. (Principal Investigator: MUDr. Jan Kopecky, DrSc.)

Abstract:

The development of new drugs and approaches for the treatment of obesity and related metabolic disorders requires accurate measurement of energy expenditure in laboratory rodents. The specific identification of components of energy expenditure, such as basal metabolic rate (BMR), thermic effect of food, thermogenesis related to physical activity and thermoregulatory energy expenditure, can be done with specific equipment available at the IPHYS, some of which has been purchased with the support of CarDIA. All this equipment has been used for the characterisation of genetically modified organisms (DEXA for body composition, indirect calorimetry with climatic chamber for energy expenditure and BMR, and IR camera, rectal probe and telemetry for body surface and core temperature respectively), for the study of adaptive thermogenesis (in addition to the above also μ PET-CT and equipment for measuring muscle performance) and for the development of new tools for the characterisation of energy metabolism (such as EMG, mechanomyography and equipment for measuring energy expenditure of isolated muscle). This complex platform allows us to develop modifications according to the specific needs of projects focused on energy homeostasis.

Selected examples of data obtained with the support of CarDia demonstrate the functioning of the techniques and provide useful data for the planned activities.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.**Work Package 2**

Bone marrow adiposity in metabolic bone diseases and osteoporosis

Molecular Physiology of Bone, Institute of Physiology, CAS, Prague

Principal Investigator: Mgr. Michaela Tencerova, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Obesity and type 2 diabetes, often accompanied by increased accumulation of bone marrow adipose tissue (BMAT), significantly impact bone homeostasis. The utilization of anti-diabetic drugs like thiazolidinediones (TZDs) exerts distinct effects on both bone and fat physiology, underscoring a dual role of shared factors present in both peripheral and bone marrow contexts. Nutrient-sensing pathways such as insulin signaling, lipid handling, are crucially involved, susceptible to metabolic disruptions, and pivotal in regulating glucose metabolism and bone homeostasis. Here, I will delve into our current findings concerning metabolic alterations in BMAT phenotype and their impact on the bone marrow microenvironment and stem cell properties in metabolic complications. Also, I will present our recent data with different interventional approaches in animal models of obesity and its effect on BMAT and

bone phenotype along with the establishment of new models of bone impairment which are part of the Cardia Project.

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Redox signaling and changes of mitochondrial cristae upon insulin secretion

Work Package 2

Laboratory of Mitochondrial Physiology (No.75), Institute of Physiology, ASCR, Prague
Principal Investigator: RNDr. Petr Ježek, DrSc.

Abstract:

Acute redox signaling from mitochondria has been sparsely reported. Fatty acid- (FA-) stimulated insulin secretion (FASIS) at low glucose by pancreatic beta-cells has been questioned. We show that FA beta-oxidation produces superoxide/H₂O₂, providing: *i*) mitochondria-to-plasma-membrane redox signaling, closing KATP-channels synergically with elevated ATP (substituting NADPH-oxidase-4-mediated H₂O₂-signaling upon glucose-stimulated insulin secretion); *ii*) activation of redox-sensitive phospholipase iPLA2gamma (termed alsoPNPLA8), cleaving mitochondrial FAs, enabling metabotropic GPR40 receptors to amplify insulin secretion (IS). At fasting glucose, palmitic acid stimulated IS in wt mice; palmitic, stearic, lauric, oleic, linoleic, and hexanoic acids also in perfused pancreatic islets (PIs), with suppressed 1st phases in iPLA2gamma-knockout mice/PIs. Extracellular/cytosolic H₂O₂-monitoring indicated knockout-independent redox signals, blocked by mitochondrial antioxidant SkQ1, etomoxir, CPT1 silencing, and catalase overexpression, all inhibiting FASIS, keeping ATP-sensitive K⁺-channels open, and diminishing cytosolic [Ca²⁺]-oscillations. FASIS in mice was a postprandially delayed physiological event. Redox signals of FA beta-oxidation are thus documented, reaching the plasma membrane, essentially co-stimulating IS. Moreover, upon glucose-stimulated insulin secretion, mitochondrial cristae became narrowed in 2D transmission electron microscopy sections, resulting from inflation of cristae volume, documented by 3D images of 2 nm resolution taken by focused-ion beam / scanning electron microscopy (FIB/SEM).

Summary: Redox signal of beta-oxidation of fatty acids plus concomitant elevation of ATP is essential for fatty-acid stimulated insulin secretion at low glucose in pancreatic beta cells.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 2

Laboratory of bioenergetics, Institute of Physiology CAS, Prague

Principal Investigator: RNDr. Tomáš Mráček, Ph.D.

Abstract:

F₀F₁-ATP synthase is the key enzyme of mitochondrial energy provision, responsible for the production of most of the cellular ATP. Recently, the DAPIT protein (Diabetes Associated Protein in Insulin sensitive Tissues) has been found to be associated with the enzyme, but its biological role is not fully characterized yet. To elucidate the importance of this novel protein we produced rat knockout of DAPIT on unique SHR background.

DAPIT^{-/-} animals were viable and possessed normal levels of fully assembled ATP synthase. However, this was predominantly present in the monomeric form. Contrary to the proposed role of ATP synthase dimers in mitochondrial cristae formation, we observed only minor changes in cristae morphology in the heart of DAPIT^{-/-} animals as well as in the HEK293 DAPIT knockdown model. We observed mild isolated ATP synthase deficiency in DAPIT^{-/-} animals, with both ADP phosphorylating and ATP hydrolyzing activities reduced by ≈10% in studied tissues, i.e. liver and heart.

DAPIT^{-/-} animals had 20-30% lower body weight and a pronounced decrease in total adiposity. Based on indirect calorimetry, DAPIT^{-/-} animals preferred the utilization of glucose to other substrates. This was replicated at the tissue level, with higher glucose oxidation in DAPIT^{-/-} skeletal muscle. Serum levels of glucose were unchanged, but DAPIT^{-/-} animals were significantly more insulin sensitive with decreased levels of serum insulin as well as area under curve in OGTT test. This is due to the improved peripheral insulin sensitivity, as glucose-stimulated insulin secretion from pancreatic islets was normal in DAPIT^{-/-} animals. High fat diet led to further dissociation of phenotype between control and knockout animals.

Conclusion:

Absence of DAPIT protein leads to preferential oxidation of glucose, increases insulin sensitivity and decreases total adiposity in the rat. This suggests that mitochondrial ATP synthase may be directly involved in the regulation of glucose homeostasis.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

WP3 Complex analytical methods and bioinformatics

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 3

Research Unit of Rare Diseases, Department of Paediatric and Adolescent Medicine, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague

Principal investigator Prof. Stanislav Kmoch

Abstract:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a disease with gradual loss of kidney function that affects about 10 % of the general population. Patients are classified into several severity-based stages according to the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) that is calculated from the serum creatinine. The eGFR values are inaccurate and they reflect relatively advanced impairment of the kidney. In our project, we have focused on plasma biomarkers of CKD in families with pathogenic variants in *UMOD* and *MUC1* genes, rare genetic causes of CKD that are autosomal dominant.

In total, we identified > 700 metabolites (lipids, polar metabolites, and exposome compounds) in 140 samples. More than 100 metabolites were significantly changed in the patients from stage 4 of the disease (with eGFR < 30 ml/min/1.73m²) compared to the controls. These patients had higher levels of creatinine, hippurates, phenol and indole derivatives, kynurenine, TMAO, CMPF, several nucleotides and nucleosides, carnitine, acylcarnitines, modified amino acids, and other compounds. Pathway enrichment analysis showed enrichment of metabolites associated with SLC-mediated transmembrane transport, metabolism of amino acids, glucose homeostasis, tryptophan catabolism, carnitine synthesis, arginine biosynthesis, and other terms. We have also calculated > 7000 ratios of polar metabolites that could serve as a proxy for the activity of metabolite conversion enzymes or transporters and correlated them with the stage of the disease in the patients.

Summary: We have characterized metabolites in patients with a well-defined cause of the kidney disease and identified metabolites that reproducibly associate with eGFR. We have found very similar metabolic profiles in UKD and MKD group. Using individuals from different stages of the disease helped us separate early and late markers of the disease and these markers can now be used for monitoring of the disease and therapeutic interventions.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 3**

Group of Laboratory of Translational Metabolism, IPHYS Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. Ing. Tomáš Čajka, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Metabolomics and lipidomics are integral parts of omics family research, primarily focusing on identifying and quantifying polar metabolites and complex lipids in biological specimens. In recent years, significant progress has been achieved in developing analytical methods to comprehensively characterize the metabolome and lipidome. This progress encompasses advancements in sample preparation, mass spectrometry-based analysis, processing of raw instrumental files, metabolite annotation, quality control measures, and bioinformatics.

Within WP3, we have streamlined a workflow for liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), facilitating simultaneous extraction of polar metabolites, complex lipids, and exposome compounds (e.g., food components, drugs) from human plasma, serum, and tissues. The sub-groups of compounds are isolated using an “all-in-one” extraction method with a mixture of methanol, methyl *tert*-butyl ether, and water. Analysis of complex lipids is conducted using reversed-phase LC (RPLC) in positive and negative electrospray (ESI) modes, while polar metabolites and exposome compounds are separated using hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC) in ESI(+) and RPLC in ESI(-). Simultaneous acquisition of MS1 and MS/MS spectra in data-dependent mode is employed for each platform.

Subsequently, the acquired raw data files are processed using MS-DIAL software. Furthermore, we have optimized current LC-MS methods to allow high-throughput analysis with an injection-to-injection time of less than 5 minutes for each sample and LC-MS platform. Additionally, spectral libraries are constructed for metabolite annotation, containing information on retention time, accurate mass (MS1), and fragmentation (MS/MS) spectra.

Summary: Recent advancements in metabolomics and lipidomics research have led to the development of streamlined LC-MS workflows enabling simultaneous extraction of polar metabolites, complex lipids, and exposome compounds, with subsequent high-throughput analysis and construction of spectral libraries for metabolite annotation.

Data obtained with CarDia support demonstrated the functioning techniques, providing useful data for planned activities.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 3**

Structure-guided analysis of pathogenic mutations: case studies

Research Unit for Rare Diseases, Department of Pediatrics and Inherited Metabolic Disorders
Aleš Hnízda, Ph.D. (PI: prof. Stanislav Kmoch)

Abstract:

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Rapid progress in DNA sequencing techniques dramatically increased our capability to explore genomes of undiagnosed patients with rare genetic diseases. Currently, major limitation is relatively low capacity and high cost of techniques needed for verification of potentially causal variants associated with diseases. Here, we show benefits of using structural analysis for the assessment of pathogenic mutations. With several case reports, we demonstrate developments of structural biology in the last decade including increased number of available structural models generated by cryo-electron microscopy and Alpha-Fold. Combining all publicly available data, we successfully assessed potential pathogenicity of mutations in several genes, and defined possible pathogenic mechanisms currently studied in follow-up studies. Here, we will present our recent cases associated with interpretation of the data from newborn screening, definition of mutation hotspots in patient cohorts and assessment of novel causative genes.

Summary: The presented data support usefulness of structural analysis in genetic examination of the patients with so far unknown rare genetic variants.

Presented activities and results obtained with CarDia support demonstrated further development of our research program within this project.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 3**

Research Unit for Rare Diseases, Department of Pediatrics and Inherited Metabolic Disorders, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University in Prague, Czech Republic
Principal Investigator: prof. Ing. Stanislav Kmoch, CSc.

Ladislav Kuchař: Management of patients with Fabry disease in the Czech Republic - from diagnosis to treatment monitoring using lipid biomarkers

Abstract:

Fabry disease (FD, OMIM 301500) is an X-linked lysosomal storage disorder caused by mutations in *GLA* gene (Xq22.1) of lysosomal α -galactosidase A (AGAL) responsible for processing substrates with terminal alpha D-galactose. The enzymatic defect leads to intra-lysosomal accumulation of globotriaosylceramide (Gb3Cer) triggering pathology cascades. Patients' management from diagnosis to treatment requires a multi-disciplinary assessment with limitations in late-onset FD phenotypes and heterozygous FD females. We focused on biochemical (lyso-Gb3Cer and AGAL activity) and genetics (XCI) markers to assess their effectivity in diagnosis, phenotype-genotype evaluation in heterozygous females and therapy monitoring of FD patients.

The study was performed in a cohort of 114 male and 162 female FD patients with classic or late-onset (e.g. cardiac) phenotype, patients with variants of unknown significance (VUS) in *GLA* gene and controls. LC-ESI-MS/MS was used to analyze plasma lyso-Gb3Cer. AGAL activity in leukocytes and plasma was measured using the standard fluorometric protocol. XCI was assessed by a combination of methylation-based and allele-specific expression assays.

Plasma lyso-Gb3Cer differentiated well groups of healthy and FD males with limitations in late-onset heterozygous FD females. Diagnostics efficacy in late-onset FD females was improved using ratio of AGAL activity to plasma lyso-Gb3Cer.

A correlation of AGAL activity and lyso-Gb3Cer concentration with XCI in cohort of 53 female patients allowed to separate patients according to phenotype (classic, late-onset, *GLA* VUS and pseudodeficiency). The results support hypothesis that biochemical and genetic markers represent the bridge for genotype-phenotype correlation in FD.

The effect of therapy was monitored by repeated analysis of plasma lyso-Gb3Cer level throughout the entire course of treatment.

Summary: The ratio of AGAL activity in plasma to plasma lyso-Gb3Cer represents the best diagnostics marker for FD females surpassing the use of solely lyso-Gb3Cer. In FD females, XCI correlates with the residual AGAL activity, plasma lyso-Gb3 levels and their ratio allowing phenotypic distribution of individuals reflecting the genetic background.

Presented data obtained with CarDia support show the new ways for management of patients with Fabry disease and good base for further research and clinical application.

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WP4 Heart rhythm disorders and their relationship to metabolic diseases

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 4 , Objective 5: To assess changes in renal and cerebral perfusion during AF

Department of Cardiology IKEM, Prague

Principal Investigators: 5.1 MUDr. Predrag Stojadinovič , 5.2 MUDr. Jana Hašková

Abstract:

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common arrhythmia in population with an incidence increasing significantly over time and with an increased age.

AF is associated with many risk factors, for example arterial hypertension, obesity, diabetes mellitus etc., which lead to development of atrial substrate and can promote AF. Hemodynamic changes caused by these risk factor and by AF itself can influence kidney or brain perfusion, and lead to their damage. There is a lack of data on the magnitude of this adverse effect of AF. Specifically, it is unknown how AF can contribute to renal dysfunction. In addition, brain perfusion may be associated with cognitive dysfunction and this has not been studied in detail.

Goal 5.1: A substudy which utilizes an intracardiac echocardiography to evaluate renal artery blood flow (RABF) during sinus rhythm (SR), induced AF and atrial pacing (AP) at the same rate.

Methods: The study enrolled 26 patients with normal serum creatine level (average 82 ± 16 $\mu\text{mol/l}$) who underwent catheter ablation for AF. Hemodynamic study assessing renal blood flow was performed during SR, pacing-induced AF and regular AP at a rate corresponding to the mean HR during AF. Renal artery and aortic velocity-time integral (VTI) were obtained by pulsed wave Doppler, and manually delineated. RABF was calculated as $r^2 \times 3.14 \times \text{VTI} \times \text{HR}$, where r is the radius of the renal artery and ascending aorta, respectively).

Results: The systolic, diastolic, right, and left atrial pressures did not significantly differ between the investigated rhythms. The mean HR during induced AF was 113 ± 21 bpm. Induction of AF led to a significant decrease in VTI in the right renal artery from 28.0 ± 8.2 cm to 16.0 ± 5.4 cm ($P < 0.01$). The mean RABF was 429 ± 147 , 411 ± 123 , and 408 ± 169 ml/min for SR, induced AF, and regular AP ($P > 0.05$), respectively, accounting for 8% of the calculated CO per one kidney. Induced AF resulted in a significant decrease in mean stroke volume (SV) from 84 ± 25 ml to 51 ± 25 ml (a relative decrease of 40%, $P < 0.001$). The change in SV was compensated by a higher HR during AF and regular AP

Conclusions: Induced AF did not cause a significant acute reduction of RABF, likely as a result of maintained systemic arterial pressure and compensation by increased HR. Whether RABF could be altered by long-term AF persistence has to be investigated by future studies.

Kidney perfusion study in patients with AF using MRI before and after electrical cardioversion is still in preparatory phase due to complexity of the MRI protocol.

Goal 5.2 Brain perfusion study in patients with AF using MRI before and after electrical cardioversion

Introduction: Our pilot data on 10 patients from previous period showed increased perfusion in the frontal and occipital regions of the brain 6,8 weeks after successful electrical cardioversion. We proposed continuation of the project with more sophisticated study protocol.

Methods: A new protocol for patients with AF requires comprehensive cognitive tests plus blood tests for markers of brain damage and brain MRI before cardioversion for AF. After cardioversion, MRI of the brain is repeated to evaluate immediate changes in perfusion plus blood tests. Three months after cardioversion, all exams, including cognitive tests is repeated.

Results: Nine patients underwent the initial exam before and after cardioversion, and three of them had three months follow-up with re-do tests. The preliminary results show us that patients with AF have below-average results on cognitive tests compared with the normal population. Similarly, brain perfusion is decreased due to AF. We documented the increment of blood perfusion in the frontal and occipital regions of the brain after cardioversion. Three months later, there is a trend to improvement of cognitive tests.

Conclusions: These pilot data suggest that there is an improvement in cognitive tests and brain blood perfusion in patients who remain in SR three months after cardioversion.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 4**

Group of the animal models of heart failure, Institute of Anatomy, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague
Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. David Sedmera, DSc.
PhD. Student (presenting author/poster): Mgr. Alena Kvasilová

Rat model of pulmonary hypertension: pathological changes on organ, tissue, cell and molecular level

Abstract:

Background:

Pressure and volume overload trigger different remodeling responses in the affected cardiac chambers. After characterizing the myocardial response to volume overload induced by aorto-caval fistula, we focus here on changes induced by severe pulmonary hypertension in the SUGEN-hypoxia model.

Methods:

Right heart pressure overload was induced by injection of SUGEN 5416 VEGF receptor inhibitor followed by hypoxic exposure (21 days) and 10 weeks in normoxia. At the sampling time, we performed transthoracic echocardiography, right heart catheterization, and sampling of the hearts for either histological evaluation, or optical mapping followed by proteomic analysis.

Results and Conclusion:

Echocardiography was inconclusive, since only right ventricle with grossly thickened wall and flattened interventricular septum was visible in the SUGEN group. Right atrial and ventricular pressures were severely increased (end-systolic 3 vs. 11 and 31 vs. 90 mm Hg, respectively). Heart weight was also significantly increased, due to more than doubling of the right atrial and ventricular wet weight (+102 and +125%, respectively). Histology showed myocyte hypertrophy in the right ventricle coupled with increased fibrosis detected by Picosirius Red (3 vs. 8% of total tissue area). Optical mapping showed a significantly slower conduction in the overloaded right ventricle. Proteomics showed the highest number of differentially expressed proteins in the right ventricle and atrium, with some similarity between SUGEN right and left ventricle; the closest to normal was the left atrium. This model illustrates compensatory changes in the right heart compartments in response to pressure overload.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.**Work Package 4, Objective 4. Randomized trial comparing catheter-based left appendage occlusion with current antithrombotic prophylaxis in patients with AF and advanced renal disease**

Principal Investigator: 4.1.and 4.2 prof MUDr. Pavel Osmančík, PhD, co-investigator: prof MUDr Josef Kautzner, CSc

Department of internal medicine, Hospital Královské Vinohrady and Department of Cardiology IKEM, Prague

Abstract:

Goal 4.1 Comparison of catheter-based left atrial appendage closure with current antithrombotic prophylaxis in patients with AF and chronic kidney disease

The current antithrombotic treatment of patients with AF and advanced kidney disease (CKD4 or CKD5) is very heterogeneous. Such patients were mostly excluded from pharmacological trials with novel anticoagulants. Recently, non-pharmacological strategies have been developed for patients with high risk of bleeding or failure of anticoagulant drugs. One of them is catheter-based left atrial appendage closure using different types of occluders. This treatment strategy has only been studied in patients with advanced kidney disease in sporadic observational studies.

Methods: The purpose of this project is to compare left atrial appendage closure with current antithrombotic practice in a randomized clinical trial. Patients from dialysis centers are randomized to left appendage closure or current antithrombotic regimen. Two Czech centres joined the multicentre randomized trial called LAA-KIDNEY, organized by Heart Centre of University Lubeck in Germany.

Results: This trial is ongoing and no results are available.

Conclusions: The trial should determine whether left appendage closure is superior to current antithrombotic regimen used in hemodialysis centres.

Goal 4.2: Study of the effects of left atrial appendage occlusion on haemodynamics and homeostasis

Introduction: There is no consensus on what kind of hemodynamic and neurohumoral changes accompanies left atrial appendage closure. Appendage closure can induce reverse atrial remodeling as well as changes in electrophysiological properties. In order to obtain more information, hemodynamic testing is performed before and after occluder insertion in the above clinical trial.

Methods: Blood pressure is measured before and after left appendage occlusion procedure at baseline and after handgrip test. Echocardiography is performed before and after the procedure. Simultaneously, blood samples are collected for serial determinations to assess the function of the different systems involved in homeostasis. Sampling is performed before and after the procedure, on the second day and at 3 months after.

Results: The preliminary results show us that patients after appendage closure have significantly higher pressures in the left atrium, both at baseline and after handgrip. NT-proBNP remains the same after three months of the follow up. Data from both centres are evaluated and recruitment of patients continues.

Conclusions: These pilot data suggest that appendage closure leads to an increase in left atrial pressures, while NT-proBNP remains the same after three months.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 4, Objective 8. To develop individualized cardiac resynchronisation therapy for patients with heart failure

Principal Investigator: doc MUDr. and Ing Karol Čurila, PhD, co-investigator: prof MUDr Josef Kautzner, CSc

Department of internal medicine, Hospital Královské Vinohrady and Department of Cardiology IKEM, Prague

Abstract:

Activity 8.1: Definition of the relationship between the nature of ventricular activation during left ventricular pacing and the efficiency of cardiac muscle work

Methods:

UHF ECG was used to visualize different activation patterns in intraventricular conduction delay versus left bundle branch block, and compared with left septal mapping with multielectrode catheter.

Results: 23 patients were evaluated, 10 of them with non-ischemic cardiomyopathy, all had QRS duration more than 140 ms. Spontaneous electrical dyssynchrony was higher in LBBB as compared to NIVCD (89 ± 17 ms vs 50 ± 23 ms). Right centricular apical pacing led to decrease of dyssynchrony in LBBB, while it increased in NIVCD. eDyssynchrony of 61 ms had 100% sensitivity and 85 % specificity to predict true LBBB.

Conclusions: UHF-ECG is a promising tool to discriminate between LBBB and INICVD.

Activity 8.2: Comparison of the hemodynamic impact of left bundle branch pacing with biventricular pacing in candidates of cardiac resynchronization therapy

Introduction: Another resynchronization therapy option is left bundle branch pacing or non-selective pacing of the left side of the interventricular septum. There are few studies that have demonstrated similar clinical evidence for left bundle branch pacing compared with biventricular pacing. Only one study has compared the hemodynamic effect of both strategies and found it to be similar.

Methods: Electrical interventricular dyssynchrony was compared with echocardiographically determined dyssynchrony. High correlation between both methods was obtained ($r=0.73$, $p<0.0001$). UHF ECG was used to compare with hemodynamic changes during right ventricular apical pacing, CRT and left bundle or left bundle area pacing. Invasive blood pressure was measured and transitions between pacing protocols were analyzed.

Results: Thirty patients with LVEF of $29 \pm 6\%$ and mean QRSd of 169 ± 24 ms were included. Twenty had non-ischemic cardiomyopathy. QRSd during BVP, LVSP, and LBBP was the same, but LBBP provided shorter LVLWd than BVP (-9 ms (-16 ; -4), $p = 0.004$); the difference between LVSP and BVP was not significant (-4 ms (-10 ; 2), $p = 0.2$). LBBP was associated with higher systolic blood pressure than BVP (4% (2 ; 5) $p < 0.001$), while LVSP was not (1% (1 ; 2), $p = 0.1$). LV hemodynamic improvements during LBBP and LVSP vs. BVP were more pronounced in non-ischemic than ischemic patients.

Conclusions: UHF-ECG allowed to document differences in LV synchrony between LBBP, LVSP, and BVP which were not observed by measuring QRSd. LBBP, but not LVSP, was associated with better LV synchrony and hemodynamics than BVP.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

WP5 Heart failure due to obesity and diabetes

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 5

Possibilities of new experimental MR equipment in IKEM, Department of Imaging Methods, IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. Ing. Daniel Jiráček, Ph.D.

Abstract:

A new experimental magnetic resonance (MR) machine, acquired from the CarDia project, has replaced a 25-year-old MR machine. Installed in November 2023, this machine boasts a magnetic field strength of 7 Tesla (7T). Its advanced features include state-of-the-art electronics and software, enabling not only standard imaging measurements (such as anatomy, angiography, and relaxometry) with high sensitivity and resolution, but also facilitating advanced MR techniques like MR diffusion, MR cardio, and X-nuclei MR.

Equipped with monitoring capabilities for vital functions, anesthesia and warming connections, and sets of radiofrequency coils for imaging mouse/rat brain and body, the machine also allows the connection of home-made coils designed and constructed in the laboratory of experimental magnetic resonance.

In this presentation, we showcase a few examples of the initial pilot results obtained from the new MR machine, including the assessment of blood flow in aortic grafts, evaluation of brown adipose tissue, examination of morphological changes in infarcted hearts, and phosphorus measurement using a home-made coil.

In summary, the installation of the new experimental 7T MR machine marks a significant advancement, offering diverse applications, including in vivo imaging, as evidenced by the data obtained with support from the CarDia project.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 5

Group of Heart failure linked to obesity and diabetes, Institute of Physiology, Prague
Principal Investigator: MUDr. František Kolář, DrSc.

Abstract:

A combination of heart and liver dysfunction worsens the prognosis of human survival. The aim of this study was to investigate whether empagliflozin (a sodium-glucose transporter-2 inhibitor) has beneficial effects on cardiac, renal and hepatic function. Adult (6-month-old) spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) were fed a high-fat diet (60% fat) for four months to induce mild heart failure and hepatic steatosis. For the last two months, the rats were treated with empagliflozin (10 mg/kg/day). High-fat diet feeding increased body weight and visceral adiposity, liver triglyceride and cholesterol concentrations, and

worsened glucose tolerance. Although the high-fat diet did not affect renal function, it significantly worsened cardiac function in a subset of SHR rats. Empagliflozin reduced body weight gain but not visceral fat deposition. It also improved glucose sensitivity and several metabolic parameters (plasma insulin, uric acid, and HDL cholesterol). In the liver, empagliflozin reduced ectopic lipid accumulation, lipoperoxidation, inflammation and pro-inflammatory HETEs, while increasing anti-inflammatory EETs. In addition, empagliflozin improved cardiac function (systolic, diastolic and pumping) without blood pressure lowering effect.

Summary: The results of our study demonstrated cardio- and hepatoprotective effects of empagliflozin in a model of heart and liver failure.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 5

Laboratory of Developmental Cardiology, Institute of Physiology of the Czech Republic, Prague
Principal Investigator: RNDr. Markéta Hlaváčková, Ph.D.

Exploring Hif-1 α and epitranscriptomic regulation in diabetic cardiomyopathy

Abstract:

Diabetes and diabetic cardiomyopathy are among the most common causes of morbidity worldwide, and their prevalence is still increasing. The mechanisms underlying diabetic cardiomyopathy pathogenesis involve changes in gene expression profiles in which epigenetic modifications of RNA (epitranscriptomics) may be involved.

In this study, we sought to explore the role of hypoxia-inducible factor 1 (HIF-1) in the alteration of the proteomic profiles of pancreatic islets and myocardial tissue after induction of type 2 diabetes mellitus and the development of diabetic cardiomyopathy. For this purpose, we used a *Hif1 α ^{+/-}* mouse model where diabetic cardiomyopathy was induced by concomitant metabolic (high-fat diet; HFD) and hypertensive stress (L-NAME-induced inhibition of NO synthase) for 8 weeks. The glucose tolerance test and blood insulin levels confirmed the development of diabetes. In both strains (wild type and *Hif1 α ^{+/-}*) of mice exposed to HFD+L-NAME, the level of glycaemia and insulin significantly increased. Moreover, glycaemia and insulin levels were significantly higher in *Hif1 α ^{+/-}* compared to wild type mice on HFD+L-NAME. Diabetic animals developed cardiac hypertrophy and their cardiac output was decreased. Proteomic analysis revealed that the cardiac proteomic profile was affected by both HFD+L-NAME and HIF-1 α deficiency, while pancreatic islets exhibited homogenous proteomic profiles among the experimental groups. Untargeted proteomic analysis showed changes in the levels of epitranscriptomic regulators either in comparison of individual strains of mice (wild type *Hif1 α ^{+/-}*) or due to HFD+L-NAME.

Summary: This research contributes to the complex mosaic of diabetes research, offering new insights into the molecular basis of diabetic cardiomyopathy and highlighting the key role of HIF-1 in the pathogenesis of this disease.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 5**

WP 5: Heart failure and metabolic status

Principal Investigator: Prof. MUDr. Vojtěch Melenovský, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Inherited cardiomyopathies (CMPs) represent an important etiology in patients with heart failure with reduced or preserved ejection fraction. Most genetic CMPs are inherited in autosomal dominant manner with incomplete penetrance. The impact of other genetic or metabolic factors on development of manifested heart failure in carriers of pathogenic or likely pathogenic (P/LP) DNA variants is in most cases neither known or even individually predictable.

Patients with cardiomyopathy receive a complex care in IKEM inclusive of genetic consultation and molecular genetic analysis after informed consent. The family cascade screening is routinely offered to relatives. The Center of inherited cardiovascular diseases is an institutional and national coordinator of cardiogenetic diagnostic and monitors the genetic architecture of cardiomyopathy on institutional and national levels.

The overall yield of P/LP DNA variants in national registry of patients (total Nr. 4955) with CMP is 30%. Most finding are in sarcomeric genes as *TTN*, *MYBPC3* or *MYH7*, followed by lamin A/C of filamin C genes. The institutional registry contains 1203 entries of patients with CMP, the genetic results correspond to national findings. During the family cascade screening we could examine 1733 relatives. The genotype positive (G+) relatives (425/1733) were offered further diagnostic work up and follow up.

Up to date, echocardiography screening in relatives revealed 12 individuals meeting diagnostic criteria of DCM and further 45 individuals with moderately reduced left ventricular ejection fraction. Performed 2 D and 3 D echocardiography results point out the indexed values of LVEDD and LVESD as the best marker of subclinical heart failure in P/LP DNA variants carriers. Further analysis of gender, BMI and other metabolic factors in identified relatives at risk is planned in order to identify the factors leading to phenotype of heart failure together with further analysis on RNA level from biopsies and explanted hearts.

Summary: The ongoing clinical, biochemical and genetic analysis on DNA and RNA levels of individuals and relatives aims to identify the factors leading to penetrance of genetic predisposition to heart failure.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12. - 13. 4. 2024.
Work Packages 2, 5, 6**

SLAVIA project from the point of view of MR image and spectrum

Dezortová M., Šedivý P, Kordač P, Burian M, Horváth L, Haluzík M, Hájek M.
IKEM, Prague

Abstract:

SLAVIA project is a randomized prospective study comparing results of different treatments of obesity. In total, 75 patients with BMI > 35 undergo laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy, endoscopic gastric plication, or conservative treatment by diet. Patients are also evaluated using magnetic resonance (MR) before and six months after the treatment. During this examination, proton MR imaging (MRI) and MR spectroscopy (MRS) of the liver are used to determine liver steatosis, MRI of abdominal area is used to calculate visceral and subcutaneous fat content, and finally, rest and dynamic phosphorus MRS of the calf muscles describe actual metabolic state of the muscles and signs of sarcopenia.

The project is in progress and data are being collected. We can expect, that changes after 6 months resulting from our three types of the obesity treatment

- 1) will be visible, but not as extensive as the results seen after one-anastomosis gastric bypass,
- 2) MR data will be able to distinguish between different types of treatment and describe their metabolic effects in more details,
- 3) changes in physical condition will be observable,
- 4) and finally, MR will be helpful in monitoring malnutrition risk and sarcopenic obesity.

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WP 6 Early atherosclerosis and atherothrombosis as its acute reversal

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 6

Early atherosclerosis and atherothrombosis, IKEM, Prague

Principal Investigator: prof. Jan Piřha, MD., PhD., FIUA, Hana Malínská, PhD., Ivana Vaněčková, PhD., DSc.

Title: Vascular changes after menopause, experimental and human perspective

Abstract:

Recent data indicate that the timing of prevention of vascular disease including atherosclerosis could be of the essence, especially in women after menopause; i.e. in population at rapidly increasing risk for cardiovascular events. The most compelling data are from hormone replacement therapy early after menopause using surrogate markers for preclinical atherosclerosis (intima media thickness in carotid arteries measured by duplex ultrasound). Nevertheless, intervention effects of traditional cardiovascular risk factors ((smoking, dyslipidemia, hypertension, (pre)diabetes)) were not studied and data regarding mechanistic explanation/biological plausibility of early cardiovascular prevention after menopause are missing.

To address this topic, we studied the effect of ovariectomy (ovx) mimicking menopause on the experimental level. In hereditary hypertriglyceridemic rat (HHTg) a model of insulin resistance and prediabetes, vascular and cardiac parameters substantially differed in their response to ovx and estradiol substitution. In the following study in the same model, the cardiovascular effects of early and late statin therapy after ovx were also not straightforward. Moreover, longer treatment with statins even led to some unfavorable changes reflecting potentially untoward effect of increased insulin resistance further potentiated by ovx and, therefore, substantially attenuating the effects of statins. In addition, in the third preliminary study in the same strain, only moderate changes of hemodynamic parameters were found; NOs mediated dilation moderately decreased after ovx, but no changes were found in sympathetic and renin angiotensin system. In pilot human studies – exercise had different effects when applied earlier after menopause and in study focused on women with type 1 diabetes time around menopause/menopausal transition indicated steeper development of unfavorable changes of markers of peripheral artery disease including toe/brachial blood pressure index and Oliva-Roztocil index (photoplethysmography method).

Summary: Data obtained with CarDia support did not demonstrate straightforward results regarding early and postponed statin treatment after ovariectomy in the experimental model of insulin resistance. In addition, only moderate hemodynamic changes were detected after ovx in the same model. Undergoing studies in women around menopause at different cardiovascular risk might offer more clear answers.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 6**

Department of Experimental Biology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno
Principal Investigator: doc. Mgr. Lukáš Kubala, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Recent discoveries have highlighted the potential role of microbiota-produced extracellular vesicles (EVs) in facilitating intercellular communication within the gut and their subsequent interaction with immune cells in the submucosa. Understanding the importance of intercellular communication between the gut microbiota, intestinal epithelium, immune cells and the arterial wall and the contribution of EVs to the induction of atherosclerotic changes will provide new opportunities for therapeutic approaches.

The aim of the presented study was to clarify the mechanism of communication mediated by EVs originating from the gut microbiome. EVs were isolated from cultures of *Enterococcus faecium* CCM 7167T and *Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus* CCM7091 using a series of centrifugation, filtration, and ultracentrifugation steps. Subsequent purification was achieved through a sucrose cushion, followed by visualization using Cryo-EM. Additional analyses included particle concentration assessment using NTA, MADLS, protein characterization via proteomics, and LTA detection through western blotting. To observe EV uptake by epithelial cells, Rhodamine B R18 staining was employed, and interactions with Caco2 cells were visualized using confocal microscopy. The impact of EVs on the inflammatory response was investigated using the RAW264.7 cell line, measuring pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines via ELISA and reactive species of nitrogen production through the Griess reaction followed by investigation into EV-receptor interactions utilized transfected HEK293 cells.

Our study's findings reveal that bacteria-derived EVs, ranging between 80 and 100 nm in diameter, contain LTA. These EVs demonstrate a potent immunostimulatory and immunomodulatory action, triggering the formation of RNS and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF-alpha and IL-6 by RAW264.7 macrophages. Moreover, our cultivation of transfected HEK293 cells with EVs suggests that the TLR2/6 heterodimer and TLR2/CD14 may serve as crucial receptors for these EVs' entrance to target cells.

The preliminary data we've obtained with CarDia support have demonstrated effective techniques that yield valuable insights for our planned experiments. Importantly, our understanding of the role of EVs in the development of atherosclerosis opens up new avenues for therapeutic approaches. By targeting microbiota modification and EV production, we could potentially revolutionize the treatment of atherosclerosis.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 6**

Mass Spectrometry, IOCB Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. RNDr. Josef Cvačka, Ph.D.

Abstract:

1. Macrophages in adipose tissue play a significant role in the development and progression of atherosclerosis. In terms of their roles in inflammation, macrophages can be classified broadly into pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory. Since the lipidome of macrophages plays a crucial role in determining their phenotype and function, we are focusing on the lipid composition of macrophage populations separated by flow cytometry. We optimized an LC-MS method for the lipidomic analysis of total lipid extract

of macrophages. Using the method, we found differences in the lipid composition of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory macrophages isolated from adipose tissues of living human kidney donors. The analysis showed a significant increase in the concentration of some lipid species in pro-inflammatory macrophages. 2. Knowing the distribution of cholesterol in tissues is crucial for better understanding various diseases. Therefore, we developed a new mass spectrometry imaging (MSI) method for localizing cholesterol in tissues. The method is based on covering tissue samples with a thin layer of silver by thermal evaporation. The deposition of an ultrathin film of silver enabled high-resolution laser desorption/ionization MSI with a pixel size of 10 μm . We used the optimized method to visualize cholesterol distribution in the brains of APP/PS1 mice model of Alzheimer's disease and myocardial sections of a human heart affected by wild-type ATTR amyloidosis.

Summary: New analytical mass spectrometry-based methods developed within the CarDia project made it possible to compare lipidomes of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory macrophages and visualize cholesterol distribution in tissues.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 6**

Functional profiling of LDL receptor gene variants

Kateřina Konečná, Jana Koutná, Lukáš Tichý, Tomáš Freiburger

Department of Clinical Immunology and Allergology – Faculty of Medicine – Masaryk University
Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. Tomáš Freiburger, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Familial hypercholesterolemia (FH) is one of the most common autosomal dominant disorders. It is characterized by elevated low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and contributes to higher risk of cardiovascular diseases. The most common cause of FH are genetic variants in the low-density lipoprotein receptor gene (LDLR). There are over 3000 known variants in the *LDLR* gene, however, the clinical significance of many variants is uncertain. The purpose of this study was to functionally characterize 16 variants in the *LDLR* gene found in patients with phenotypic FH to help determine their pathogenicity. This information will be useful for identifying disease-causing variants in patients with phenotypic FH, allowing for cascade testing of potentially affected relatives.

We performed *in vitro* functional assays based on transient expression of wild-type and mutant LDL receptors in LDLR-deficient Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells. To analyze the relative amount of LDL receptors expressed on the cell surface (compared to a WT control), we labeled live cells with fluorescently tagged anti-LDLR antibody and analyzed fluorescence intensity by flow cytometry. To further determine the effect of the studied variants on the whole LDLR cycle, we analyzed the ability of mutant LDL receptors to internalize labeled LDL particles using flow cytometry. We also analyzed the expression and maturation of LDLR protein in transfected CHO cells by Western blot.

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Based on maturation, surface expression of LDLR and internalization of LDL particles, we concluded that out of 16 studied variants, 11 variants caused lowered cell surface expression of LDLR (10-75% of WT), 2 variants caused severely lowered expression of LDLR on the cell surface (<10% WT), one variant exhibited normal expression on the cell surface coupled with deficient internalization of LDL particles, and two variants did not affect LDLR function.

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WP 7 Influencing acute and chronic complications of diabetes by organ and tissue transplantation

**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4. 2024.
Work Package 7**

Vascular substitutes: Cooperation between IKEM and the Institute of Anatomy, First Faculty of Medicine,
Charles University

Principal Investigators: MUDr. Jaroslav Chlupáč, Ph.D., MUDr. Jan Frank

Abstract:

The saphenous vein graft (SVG) is the most frequently utilized vascular graft in coronary artery bypass surgery and peripheral vascular surgery for critical limb-threatening ischemia and diabetic foot syndrome. A saphenous vein, a nonessential superficial vein, can be harvested from the patient's lower extremities. Any vein engrafted into arterial circulation undergoes remodeling, potentially resulting in vein graft disease (VGD). External stenting devices have shown considerable effectiveness in preventing VGD in animal models and in some clinical trials regarding coronary revascularization, though reports in peripheral surgery are scarce.

The aim of our study was to examine the effect of the external mesh FRAME (VGS, Israel), intended for peripheral vascular surgery, in an animal model. The experiments were carried out at the IKEM facility. This model involved the reversed interposition grafting of internal jugular veins (IJVs) to common carotid arteries in female domestic pigs (n = 7) for one month. We did not use SVGs in pigs due to anatomical and physiological differences between bipeds and quadrupeds, opting instead for IJVs. Four IJV grafts were externally supported with FRAME, while seven IJV grafts served as unsupported controls. The grafts were examined through macroscopy, angiography, flowmetry, and microscopy at explantation.

All FRAME-supported grafts remained patent, whereas four of the seven control grafts became occluded. The presence of metal material in explanted tissues precludes conventional histological examinations. Our institute lacks the technology for resin-embedding and sectioning with a tungsten carbide blade. With assistance from colleagues at the Institute of Anatomy (Prof. Sedmera, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University), the explanted samples were visualized through confocal microscopy and macro photography by microscope at their facility. Additionally, electron microscopy was also conducted (Dr. Benada, Institute of Microbiology, Czech Academy of Sciences). We measured the area and thickness of neo-intimal hyperplasia (NIH) in our serial sections through digital analysis of high-resolution macroscopic images. As a result, a significant reduction of NIH in FRAME-supported grafts was observed.

Summary: The current-generation external support device FRAME improved patency and significantly mitigated the formation of neo-intimal hyperplasia in our porcine internal jugular vein-to-carotid artery model. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time, external stenting technology has been tested in this particular in vivo model, despite the abundance of previous pre-clinical experimentation. The collaboration with the Institute of Anatomy, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, provided us with alternative imaging modalities for metal-containing arterial samples and suggested novel techniques for measuring neo-intimal hyperplasia.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4. 2024.
Work Package 7**

Vascular substitutes: Cooperation with the Institute of Physiology, Czech Academy of Sciences
Principal Investigators: MUDr. Jan Frank, MUDr. Jaroslav Chlupáč, Ph.D.

Abstract:

We are attempting to find new vascular substitutes and test them in a living animal model. Recent studies have shown promising results in colonizing tissues with Wharton's jelly mesenchymal stem cells (WJSCs). Along with colleagues from the Institute of Physiology at the Czech Academy of Sciences, we are trying to colonize porcine pericardia with WJSCs and use them as vascular patches in porcine carotid arteries.

The first phase was underway at the Institute of Physiology. In an in vitro environment, colleagues recolonized decellularized porcine pericardia using different surface modalities such as radiation, vascular growth factors, heparin, and fibrin. Four types of patches were created: two of them were seeded with WJSCs, and two were unseeded controls.

The second phase was carried out at IKEM, where we implanted the vascular patches into porcine carotid arteries. During the procedure, we measured blood flow in the artery before and after implantation to check for patency. One month later, we performed angiography to verify if the implants were open. Afterward, we explanted the carotid arteries along with the patches. We then cut these samples into a series of cross-sections and examined them macroscopically. The next step was to preserve them in formalin and send them for histological examination.

The next step will be the evaluation of histological samples, where we measure the degree of intimal hyperplasia, which is a typical sign of negative remodeling, and then compare the degrees of hyperplasia among various vascular substitutes. Another aspect we are examining is endothelialization.

Summary: We tested four types of vascular patches in porcine carotid arteries, each three times. All patches remained open as expected because in patch arterioplasty setting, only half of the vessel is prone to intimal hyperplasia, even though the hyperplasia covered the entire lumen of the vascular patch. In two patches, we found an aneurysm, which is a typical complication of decellularized tissues. We did not observe substantial macroscopical differences between patches modified with given biochemical or cellular surface modalities.

Regarding microscopical examinations, we are gathering data from histology to compare the thickness of intimal hyperplasia on our samples. Furthermore, scaffold modifications with better structural integrity are warranted.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 7: Transcriptomic examination in diabetic kidney donors and pancreatic grafts

Transplant Center IKEM, Prague

Transplant Laboratory IKEM, Prague

Alberta Transplant Applied Genomic Centre, Canada

Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. O. Viklický, CSc., doc. MUDr. P. Girman, Ph.D., doc. Mgr. P. Hrubá, Ph.D.

Abstract:

The use of diabetic donors for kidney transplantation has increased; however, the question of the transfer of diabetic nephropathy from donor to kidney recipient remains unanswered. Therefore, gene expression profiling using microarray was used to first identify transcripts associated with diabetic nephropathy by comparing kidney donors with (n=43)/without diabetes (n=86). Four intrarenal transcripts (*AKR1C2*, *AKR1B10*, *NQO1*, and *SERPINF2*) able to discriminate donor diabetes with AUC =0.81 were identified. Their expression 3 months after transplantation from diabetic to non-diabetic recipients normalized. Those transcripts are probably induced by chronic hyperglycemia and might have a protection role against overloading with oxide radicals.

Transcriptomic evaluation of rejection in kidneys and hearts using Molecular Microscope® Diagnostic System (MMDx) is available in Transplant laboratory since 2022 and is used in clinical practice. However, MMDx has not been validated for use in pancreatic grafts. The MMDx algorithm for pancreatic grafts will be created in collaboration with Alberta Transplant Applied Genomic Centre and requires large reference set of measured pancreases. IKEM as one of the most active centers in the world, with available MMDx technology, has already analyzed 77 pancreatic samples by MMDx. Only in 11 out of 77, molecular rejection was confirmed using MMDx kidney algorithm. Differential expression analysis between samples with rejection in histology (n=36) vs. no-rejection (n=35), showed upregulation of inflammatory response (p=2.8E-17), antigen-processing and presentation (p=3.7E-14) and regulation of T-cell activation (p=5.3E-14) in samples with rejection.

Summary: We were able to detect early diabetic changes on a molecular level in donor kidneys without markable histologic signs of diabetic nephropathy. After transplantation of diabetic donor kidney into non-diabetic recipients, their expression normalized, supporting safety of this approach. Molecular assessment of pancreatic graft showed less rejection than histology, but sample size still needs to be larger to develop valid MMDx algorithm.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 7

Group of Insulin Producing Tissue Transplantation IKEM, Prague

Principal Investigator: doc. MUDr. Jan Kříž, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Cell cycle of pancreatic beta cells

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Klára Zacharovová, Kateřina Bittenglová, Tomáš Koblas, Jan Kříž

Pancreatic beta-cells proliferate extremely slowly in adults. Therefore, very little is known about their cell cycle. Our laboratory is involved in experiments to stimulate beta cell proliferation in vitro, which allows us to study their cell cycle. Detailed information on the beta cell cycle could help to more precisely schedule proliferative stimuli.

Our group has developed a method based on transfection of cells by mRNA in order to temporarily stimulate the production of cyclins and their kinases. Dissociated rat pancreatic islet cells – single cell suspension - then achieve approximately 80% rate of proliferation. The cell cycle is analysed by flow cytometry using markers that are specific to its individual phases. We also use the incorporation of the artificial nucleotide EdU, which is incorporated into DNA during S phase and can be easily detected by fluorescent labelling.

The most active of the mRNA transfected beta cells entered G1 phase in 1 hour and G1 takes approximately 13 hours. Part of the cells entered S phase in 14 hours and it takes about 8 hours. And the G2+M phase starts 20 hours after transfection and lasts about 4 hours.

In future experiments, we are going to use inhibitors of specific cell cycle phases. These inhibitors allowed us to describe the timing of cell cycle phases more precisely.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 7

Group of Insulin Producing Tissue Transplantation IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. MUDr. Jan Kříž, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Transplantation of pancreatic islets into a diabetic rat can normalize blood glucose levels. The local response of liver tissue to islet transplantation varies in different strains of rats. A possible explanation for this problem may lie in the different reactivity of liver cells to insulin in insulin-sensitive and resistant animals. Another reason may lie in the different reactivity of the insulin receptor to species self/different insulin. A simple experiment was designed to address this question.

The difference between reactivity of Brown Norway (BN-insulin sensitive) rats on human vs rat (Ins1+Ins2 = 1:1) insulins and the difference between reactivity of BN and hHTG (insulin resistant) rats on human insulin were tested. Using Western Blotting the phosphorylated forms of Akt-kinase were measured in liver tissue 1, 3, 5, and 10 minutes after i.v. injection of insulin. Stimulation indexes in their maximum

were 2.5x higher in HTG compared to BN rats after Human insulin injection and rat insulins stimulated Akt-kinase phosphorylation 3x more than human insulin in BN rats.

Summary: The measured data confirm the different reactivity of rats on human vs rat insulins, and different rat strains on human insulin.

Selected sample of data obtained with CarDia support demonstrated the functioning techniques providing useful data for planned activities.

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Posters section

Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 2

Laboratory of Translational and Experimental Diabetology and Obezitology IKEM, Prague

Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. Martin Haluzík, DrSc.

The role of modulation of cellular senescence in the metabolic effects of bariatric surgery

Tereza Havrlantova¹, Igor Simonik², Iveta Pleyerova¹, Renata Pavlovicova¹, Miloslava Cechova¹, Milos Mraz³, Sona Stemberkova Hubackova^{1*} and Martin Haluzik^{1,3*}

¹Centre for Experimental Medicine, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic, ²St. Zdislava Hospital, Mostiste, ³Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

Introduction: Bariatric surgery represent the most efficient approach to treatment of obesity, however the detailed mechanism of its positive metabolic effect beyond weight loss is still not fully understood. Cellular senescence arrests the damaged cells thus prevent further spreading of the damage. However, excessive persistence of senescent cells especially in adipose tissue can contribute to subclinical inflammation and development of type 2 diabetes and other chronic metabolic diseases. Our study explored the effects of bariatric surgery on the circulating markers of cellular senescence and the presence of senescent cells in adipose tissue before and after surgery.

Methods: 47 patients with obesity (2nd grade and higher) with or without type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) indicated to bariatric surgery (sleeve gastrectomy) were included into the study. Subcutaneous (SAT) adipose tissue and plasma samples were collected during the surgery (V1) and 6 month after the surgery (V3). The analysis of samples included RT-qPCR (mRNA transcription in SAT) and standard biochemical methods, ELISA or Luminex for detection of hormones and other relevant parameters in plasma.

Results: Bariatric surgery reduced amount of senescent cells in adipose tissue (57% reduction) along with decreased oxidative stress and markers of inflammation. Decreased recruitment of pro-inflammatory macrophages as measured by RT-qPCR was also observed. In addition, we detected lower plasma level of soluble E-selectin (31.3+/-14.0 ng/ml vs. 22.6+/-11.4 ng/ml, p=0.03), ICAM-1 (387.4+/-98.7 ng/ml vs. 338.6 vs. 92.5 ng/ml, p=0.04) and Galectin 3 (12.6+/-8.6 ng/ml vs. 10.0+/-4.9 ng/ml, p=0.12), a molecules enhancing cardiovascular damage known to be produced by senescent cells, as well decreased plasma level of ACE2 (1.6+/-1.9 ng/ml vs. 0.8+/-1.4 ng/ml, p=0.04), whose increased production was detected in senescent cells. Importantly, we observed decreased expression of *ADAM17* in SAT, which plays crucial role in making a soluble form of ACE2, currently representing a new predictor of cardiovascular damage.

Conclusions: Reduction of senescent cells in adipose tissue after bariatric surgery could contribute to improvement of inflammation and metabolic parameters in patients with obesity and decreases the risk of cardiovascular complications.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 2

Laboratory of Translational and Experimental Diabetology and Obezitology IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. Martin Haluzík, DrSc.

Reduction of cellular senescence decreases the risk of diabetic kidney disease

Ondrej Zizka,¹ Tereza Havrlantova,² Jan Stursa,¹ Petra Skaroupkova,² Renata Pavlovicova,¹ Petr Svoboda,^{2,3} Vojtech Skop,¹ Barbora Judita Kasperova,^{1,4} Klara Bohacova,⁵ Ludek Cervenka,² Lukas Werner,¹ Martin Haluzik,^{2,*} and Sona Stemberkova Hubackova,^{1,5*}

¹Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic. ²Centre for Experimental Medicine, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic. ³Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Prague, Czech Republic. ⁴First Faculty of Medicine, Charles

Introduction: Despite extensive research, limited efficacy of current therapies used for patients with obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) have prompted a search for novel therapeutic options, such as targeting cellular senescence. Our goal was therefore to test the Mitochondria-targeted Tamoxifen (MitoTam), a potential anti-cancer agent with senolytic activity, on pathologies related to T2DM.

Methods: C57BL/6 male mice (n=7-10) fed with **SD** (standard diet for 8 month), **HFD** (high fat diet for 8 month) were treated with MitoTam (**MT**; 2 mg/kg dissolved in 4 % ethanol in corn oil) or the vehicle (**CO**) given i.p. twice per week for a period of 4 weeks, Metformin (**Met**; 250mg/kg in PBS) or Finerenone (**Fin**; 2.5mg/kg in PBS) given p.o. daily for 28 days and Empagliflozin (**EMPA**; 10mg/kg i food) given p.o. daily for 5 weeks.

Results: Our data show, that compared to non-treated mice with diet induced obesity and T2DM MitoTam improved glucose parameters, with most pronounced reduction of visceral adipose tissue. Glucose-lowering effect of MitoTam was linked to improvement of T2DM-related hormones profile and was accompanied by reduced lipid accumulation in liver. Lower senescent cell burden in various tissues also resulted in lower level of circulating inflammatory mediators that enhance metabolic dysfunction. Moreover, decreased presence of senescent cells reduced kidney fibrosis, a frequently occurring complication of T2DM that worsens its progression. Compared to standard anti-diabetic therapies (Metformin, Empagliflozin), mice treated with MitoTam showed lower accumulation of fibrotic cell and microenvironment in kidney followed by decreased kidney injury and secretion of injury molecules playing negative role in development of cardiovascular diseases in patients with obesity and T2DM. Compared to Finerenone, an established anti-fibrotic therapy reducing kidney failure, MitoTam not only prevents expression of fibrotic proteins, but also eliminates fibrotic cells.

Conclusions: Reduction of senescence by the senolytic agent MitoTam shows complex effect on improvement of metabolic parameters and reduction of renal fibrosis and damage compared to established anti-diabetic or anti-fibrotic therapies. MitoTam thus represents promising strategy for treatment of obesity and type 2 diabetes and their complications like diabetic kidney disease.

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Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.

Work Package 2

Laboratory of Translational and Experimental Diabetology and Obesity, Experimental Medicine Centre, Institute of Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague
Principal Investigator: prof. MUDr. Martin Haluzík, DrSc.

Type 2 Diabetes Patients Adherence to Pharmacotherapy in the Czech Republic

Vojtěch Škop^{1,2}, Ivana Laňková³, Petr Svoboda^{1,2}, Simona Antalová⁴, Štěpánka Franková³, Kateřina Malá⁵, Josef Malý⁵, Martin Haluzík^{1,3*}

¹Experimental Medicine Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic; ²Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic; ³Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁴Institutional pharmacy, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁵Department of Social and Clinical Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic. *Correspondence: Martin Haluzík, halm@ikem.cz

Introduction: Adherence to treatment plays a crucial role in achieving therapeutic outcomes. However, an estimated one-quarter of patients fail to take their prescribed medications, placing a significant burden on the healthcare system and exacerbating patients' conditions. Methods of studying adherence, particularly those relying on questionnaire data, are known to be inaccurate. Direct methods, based on monitoring the presence of pharmaceuticals in the blood, offer greater explanatory value. Currently, however, there is no available data on adherence of type 2 diabetes patients in the Czech Republic to pharmacotherapy obtained using direct methods. Here, we used direct measurements of blood concentrations of metformin and other drugs in patients with type 2 diabetes to study their adherence.

Methods: In this cross-sectional study, we monitored the presence of 40 drugs in the blood of 546 type 2 diabetes patients. Metformin was a common drug for all patients. Blood samples from patients were obtained during regular outpatient visits, during which patients also completed a questionnaire on medication use.

Results: The level of metformin in the blood of patients increased with the prescribed dose and decreased with the time elapsed since the last intake. Metformin was not detected in the blood of 13 patients at all, and only subtherapeutic levels (<100 ng/ml) were found in another 29 patients. There was no significant difference in glycemia, HbA1c, insulinemia, and subclinical inflammation parameters between patients with therapeutic and subtherapeutic concentrations of metformin. To assess the reliability of questionnaire responses, we further focused on the presence of smoking products in the blood. Out of a total of 163 patients in whom the nicotine metabolite was detected, 61 reported being non-smokers.

Conclusion: Patients in the Czech Republic appear to be highly adherent to metformin treatment. However, concealing information in questionnaires suggests that adherence could be lower. Further analysis, particularly involving other prescribed medications and considering questionnaire responses along with duration of diabetes, will enhance the accuracy of the results. Moreover, data from direct methods may be distorted by its use only prior to blood sampling, which represents a limitation of this method for adherence studies.

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**Off-Site meeting of CarDia; Olomouc, Czech Republic, 12.-13.4.2024.
Work Package 7**

Group of Insulin Producing Tissue Transplantation IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. MUDr. Jan Kříž, Ph.D.

Pancreatic islets injury by electroporation with and without siRNA

Tomšovská V., Fábryová E., Leontovyč I., Plecítá L., Holendová B., Veřtátová M., Girman P., Kříž J

Abstract:

Background: Microporation is a modification of electroporation technique, which can be used for introduction of macromolecules into pancreatic islet cells. Using short electric pulses, the micro pores within a cellular membrane are created. Nucleic acids can subsequently enter the cell. We tested, potential detrimental effects of microporation as a transfection method for siRNA introduction into pancreatic islet (PI) cells.

Methods: Male Brown Norway rats 10 – 12 weeks old were used as a donor of PI. PI were isolated by collagenase digestion according to a standard protocol. After overnight cultivation, microporation was used as transfection method (Neon, 2 pulses, 950 V, 30 ms). There were 3 samples: PI microporated with 200 nM siRNA, microporated without siRNA, and nontreated PI. After 24 h cultivation, islets were subjected to tests of viability and function – perifusion insulin release test, oxygen consumption rate, fluorescent test of membrane integrity (propidium iodide and acridine orange) to identify live and dead cells.

Results: All of the used methods didn't show significant differences among treated PI versus nontreated control. The insulin release during perifusion test and oxygen consumption rate (after stimulation by glucose in high concentration) were not impaired. Using fluorescent test of membrane integrity, the percentages of dead cell in PI were: 15,9 % after microporation with siRNA, 13,7% after microporation and 10,6 % in control PI.

Conclusions: Microporation with or without siRNA did not impair PI. Microporation appears to be a safe method for transfection of PI.

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Group of Insulin Producing Tissue Transplantation IKEM, Prague
Principal Investigator: doc. MUDr. Jan Kříž, Ph.D.

Abstract:

Cryopreservation of dissociated rat pancreatic islet cells

Klára Zacharovová, Kateřina Bittenglová, František Saudek, Jan Kříž

Long-term cultivation of isolated islets leads to dedifferentiation of endocrine cells or their death. Cryopreservation of whole islets is a technically demanding process. To preserve islet cells for later use, we have developed a method for cryopreservation of dissociated rat pancreatic islet cells.

Isolated rat pancreatic islets were dissociated into cell suspension by Accutase (20 min, RT). Some cells were used fresh and some were frozen by controlled cooling in CMRL medium supplemented with 20% FBS and 10% DMSO. Frozen samples were stored in liquid nitrogen until next usage. Fresh and thawed cells were tested for viability by Vi-CELL XR Cell Viability Analyzer (Beckman Coulter) and seeded into 96 well plate coated with extracellular matrix produced by bladder cancer cells (HTB-9), 50 000 cells per well. Cultivated cells were tested for glucose stimulated insulin secretion. Subsequently, beta and alpha cell were immunolabeled to analyse their occurrence.

Viability of thawed cells was slightly lower than that of fresh cells, (54% versus 56%). Glucose stimulated insulin secretion was comparable in thawed and fresh cells, stimulation index was 3 and 3.5, respectively. Cultivated dissociated cells successfully adhered on the coated surface of culture plate and both beta cells and alpha cells were represented among them in similar ratio, in frozen samples there were 32 alpha cells per 100 beta cells and in fresh samples 37 alpha cells per 100 beta cells.

The results of this preliminary study show that cryopreserved dissociated rat islet cells have comparable functional quality to fresh cells. This approach represents a simple method for long-term preservation of islet cells.

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